
ANALYZING OF PRAGMATIC ACTIVITIES FOR THE SPEAKING CLASSROOM

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this article is to demonstrate how to identify pragmatic teaching points, to introduce related activities, and to generally encourage attention to pragmatic speaking ability in language classrooms. This article promotes the idea that pragmatic skills identified and developed in EFL settings contribute to communicative success.

Keywords: *pragmatic teaching, linguistic options, linguistic choices, language functions, pragmatic research.*

Being able to speak naturally and appropriately with others in a variety of situations is an important goal for many English as a foreign language EFL learners. Because the skill of speaking invariably involves interaction with people and using language to reach objectives, it is crucial for teachers to explore activities that help students learn the typical ways to express these and other language functions.

To interact successfully in myriad contexts and with many different speakers, learners need to develop a repertoire of practical situation-dependent communicative choices. The study of how language is used in interactions is called pragmatics, and while appropriate interactions come naturally to native speakers of a language, EFL learners need to be aware of the many linguistic and strategic options available to them in certain situations. Through pragmatics is an extensive field within linguistics, much pragmatic research has focused on speech acts performed by learners and the linguistic and strategic choices they employ. To use pragmatically appropriate speech, EFL users must account for not only the form and function of a second language, but the context as well. In doing so, they will be more comfortable speaking to interlocutors who may vary in age, gender, social class, and status. Special conversational choices are also required based on the relationship between speakers—whether they know each other and for how long. In addition, conversational expectations and desired objectives can influence linguistic and strategic choices of

what to say. The ability to account for and adjust to these variables when speaking English defines one’s pragmatic competence.

Despite its importance in EFL communication, the teaching of pragmatics is often overlooked in the classroom and underrepresented in teaching materials and teacher education courses. Reasons include insufficient class time, lack of interest, or inadequate recognition of its importance in interpersonal communication. There may also be a shortage of practical and achievable activities for the classroom that introduce and promote the development of such nuanced language use. While teachers may recognize the importance of pragmatics and want to use it in their lesson, many are unsure how to select and incorporate pragmatic teaching activities in EFL classes. This seems to be the case in my country, where I teach, and I suspect the situation is similar in other EFL contexts.

It begins by discussing pragmatics as a general field within EFL education before moving on to present the notion of speech act sets, which are step-by-step conversational options normally used to successfully communicate a variety of language functions. Speech act sets are considered valuable tools for examining language and strategies choices made during speech production, and they also provide useful templates for language teachers who want to add pragmatic elements to their speaking lessons; as such, the concept of SASs for the language functions of apologizing and requesting, this article demonstrates how to identify specific pragmatic instruction. This article also suggests classroom activities that teachers can use to help learners develop and refine their pragmatic abilities in English. Pragmatic has been defined as “the study of language from the point of view of users, especially the choices they make and the effect their use of language has on other participants in the act of communication”. The aspect of “choice” and “effect” are particularly relevant for achieving for desired outcomes during interpersonal communication. In terms of pragmatic choices, EFL learners need to be aware of the many linguistic and strategic options they can use in certain circumstances. The linguistic options will likely differ from their first language, depending on the cultural background, the strategic alternatives in English also be different. Regarding “effect,” learners need to understand the ramifications of utilizing different linguistic options in certain situations and contexts. Speakers are required to consider options and select among alternatives to produce contextually appropriate speech. For instance, speaking to a friend in a cafe about a low test score may necessitate different language and strategies than talking about the same topic to the instructor who graded the test.

Apologizing about forgetting a meeting with the potential employer would likely involve a different level of formality than if the meeting were with a close friend. Complaints to a colleague of the rank about working conditions would probably come out differently if made to the manager. Such situations call for the ability to operate within pragmatic norms, which are “range of tendencies or conventions for pragmatic language use that are typical or generally preferred in the second language community.

Failure to adhere to these norms may lead to unintended consequences and unequal treatment of the speaker. On the other hand, culturally appropriate choices when interacting with different subgroups will potentially lead to more positive experiences, increased motivation, and appealing outcomes for learners. Based on this line of thinking, the following questions may be of interest to educators involved in intercultural communication and speaking classes:

- Do students have an appropriate linguistic and strategic range to vary their speech depending on context.

- Do they understand the consequences of using one utterance or strategy over another?

- How can pragmatic instructions be implemented in second language classroom?

It is important for students to be conscious of their options and the consequences that result from appropriate and inappropriate choices. Even though first language partners for language functions may differ from second language partners, learners will benefit from familiarity with appropriate second language SAs. This awareness will allow them to communicate within standard organization patterns that native language users expect, although language learners may not always have the goal of attaining native-like fluency, and the relevance of “native speaker” norms is changing. However, given the importance may want to include pragmatic elements in lessons. SAs offer a straightforward way of identifying specific areas in need of development and assessing pragmatic output.

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